

Impact of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness of Watches in Ahmedabad City

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of social media marketing on brand awareness of watches in Ahmedabad city. In an age where digital platforms help shape consumer perceptions, to understand the dynamics of social media marketing's impact on brand awareness becomes critical for a business, such as competing watches. To what extent social media marketing strategies have contributed to the visibility and recognition of the brand in the local market. The research uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to find out. The main purpose of this study is to understand the effectiveness of different platforms to reach and engage the target audience including but not limited to Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter but different social media platforms, etc Focuses and surveys. For brand awareness, social media actions are analyzed to measure the relationship between frequency, type of content shared, and consumer engagement with brand awareness. As such the findings are intended to provide value for the Ahmedabad operating watches brand, which is used to increase their brand visibility and prepare their social media strategy. This study not only contributes to the academic community on the relationship between social media marketing and brand awareness but also provides implications for businesses seeking to optimize digital marketing efforts in the specific context of the watch industry in Ahmedabad city. As consumer behavior is constantly evolving in this digital age, all research marketing strategies should address the timely user reviews that are significant to the success of a watch brand in the local market has the effect

INTRODUCTION

Social media is the innovation of today's world where social media has become a way where all retailers can easily reach a wide range of customers. It can also demonstrate efforts to engage more customers, which work between brands and buying and selling. As the rise of social media trust helps an organization use new ways of communicating with its customers, it is easy to find ways to use trust in social media. (Mangold and Faulds 2009)

Market Insights:

There were many wristwatch segments, around 80% of the Indian watch market. In India, the wristwatch market is valued at INR 94.55 Bn in 2018 it is expected to reach INR 192.74 Bn in 2024. expanding a compound annual growth rate is 13.21% during the predicted period (2019-2024).

In recent years smartwatches and premium watches have had dramatic growth, which has demand and popularity. The components have contributed to the significant growth of the wristwatch market. Ripped goods and service tax (GST) Price on luxury watches is increasing due to fashion awareness among the consumer we have rapid market growth. Making progress in the retail landscape and increasing in Internet retailing selling of wristwatches is expected a good experience to increase in the Indian market. Most of the company has also developed fitness bands and trackers in smartwatch to boost the wristwatch market.

Market Segment Analysis:

Technology has segmented the wrist watch market in India based on the price range of the products and its economic price into premium price segment. In India this segment is mostly driven by the unorganized sector. And in this system the customer of the price segment The base is also high. It also includes the population of the country. As the revenue generated from the sale of products in the price segment within the economy was seen as ~37.95% of the revenue in the market in 2018. And now the demand for premium branded watches accelerated by ~13.75% during this period. It has been assumed. Consumers are also getting interested in social media.

Competition Analysis:

Some of the major players in this market include Titan Company Limited, Casio India Co.private Limited, and Rolex Watch Company. Among these skilled players, the industry is led by Titan Company Limited, As a strategic move to capture around 40% share of the wristwatch market, all the players are trying to diversify their products by introducing smartwatches. While the overall sales volume of smartwatches in India in 2019 was around 34,200 units. And companies are looking forward to the future with new features and technology. The Competition is likely to Improve in the Future.

Companies Covered:

Watch companies like Timex Group India Limited, Titan Company Limited, Casio India Co. Pvt. Ltd., Citizen Watch Pvt. Ltd., Fossil India Pvt. Ltd., PA Time Industries Rolex Watch Company Pvt. Ltd., and Swatch Group Pvt. Ltd. are the companies which have established themselves as good brands today.

Research Objective

- 1) Analyze the social media usage patterns among the target audience in Ahmedabad.
- 2) Examine the level of customer engagement on social media platforms.
- 3) Measure the current level of brand awareness of watches in Ahmedabad.
- 4) Assess the effectiveness of social media in driving customer actions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Kumari, K. (2022) In this pandemic situation, businesses and brands have good news on social media which can benefit both big and small brands. Once you know the numbers, it's easy to understand why businesses and the consumer market agree that social media is an essential platform for building brands. Therefore this study aims to identify the social media marketing effects on brand awareness and brand identity loyalty of consumers. Because the concept of analyzing the mediating effect of brand awareness continues to receive more attention from the marketing academy. This research method is done according to the problem of convenience sampling. Based on data collected from social media users in Sri Lanka, equation modeling has been used for analysis. This result shows that social media marketing influences brand awareness and brand loyalty, and it influences brand loyalty. It further proves the findings that brand recognition can improve customer loyalty through social media marketing, which is promoted through social media. Social media increases the brand, so the brand's reach increases so consumers can remember the brand. Research shows how action reacts when apparel companies listen to conversational hiccups with social media while building brand awareness.

Schivinski, B., & Dabrowski, D. (2015) Purpose - In the purpose of this article, Facebook generates consumer-based brand equity (CBBE) metrics in the form of social media communication effects. It fills the gap as a design approach. All of the tests were conducted online on the quality and brand loyalty of consumers in general social media brand communication.

Different industries like beverages, clothing, and mobile have done a well-structured investigation of social media in an examination of the difference in consumer perception of brand equity metrics. Brand Communication Brand awareness and influence.

Ebrahim, R. (2020) Within this era, abstract social media platforms have become integrated with the creation of marketing. This new technology sets up new communication tools, and the potential to engage with customers to react and trust them. The purpose of this study is to find out the effects of social media marketing on brand equity. In an online survey of 151 users of the following telecommunication companies on social media based in Egypt, the structural equation, the model, and the data collected using it were analyzed. In which the result shows that there are only three activities which are trendiness, customization, and word-of-mouth. The achievement of brand loyalty in social media. And equity is indirectly affected, this study emphasizes the role of trust and provides comprehensive guidance in measuring the effectiveness of social media marketing.

Ansari, S., Ansari, G., Ghori, M., & Kazi, A. (2019) The purpose of this study was mainly to examine and examine the effects of brand awareness and social media content marketing on consumer purchase decisions. From which the data for this research has been collected through an online questionnaire. The total number for this study was 151 (45% females; 55% males), and the purpose was to examine the relationship between consumers and social media marketing. The results show that there is a weak positive significant relationship between purchase decision, It is assumed to have a moderate positive significant relationship with the overall purchase decision of consumers in the social media content market.

Midha, N., Yadav, S., & Srivastava, S. (2021)

Social media has become an essential part of today's world. The business world has also seen numerous opportunities in its application. This paper studies the effectiveness of social media marketing on brand equity for white goods in India Design, Methodology This study approaches social media and brand equity through the ISMBE model (babac,2011). and explores the impact of variables on brand equity in India. The researcher looked past social media and brand equity to solve standardized questions drawn from studies that were administered to a random sample of 151 respondents using Google Forms. Various tests were applied to verify the variables, which were on reliability and validity. In which it was analyzed using a line key. And finally, equations were established to understand the effect of variables independently. Conclusions - This study helps build social media marketing equity. So the emphasis within the study is, That should be considered for consumers through social media as a cost to build and strengthen white goods and brand equity. The findings support the framework in the ISMBE model. The value of social media marketing and its areas of little research and impact on equity. While past research has dealt with categories like mobile, fashion mall but there is no study on the impact of social media variables on brand equity in India thus contributing to the understanding. Social media marketing in India, honeycomb model, based brand equity, identity, conversation, sharing, relationship, frustration, anxiety, research paper etc .

Hypothesis Testing

H1: There is significant association between age of respondent and I use social media platforms [eg. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter] regularly.

H2: There is significant association between age of respondent and I am aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media.

H3: There is significant association between age of respondent and Social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands.

H4: There is significant association between age of respondent and I am more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social media.

H5: There is significant association between age of respondent and The quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands.

METHODOLOGY

Type of research : Primary research
 Research design : Descriptive research design
 Participants : People living in Ahmedabad city
 Area of research : Ahmedabad
 No. of respondents : 151
 Sampling method : Non - probability- Convenient sampling
 Data collection method : Questionnaire - Google form
 Analysis collected data : MS Excel

RESULT

Demographic Summary

The data presents information on the demographic distribution of a sample group based on age, gender, and educational background.

Age:

- 55.6% of the participants fall in the 18-20 age range.
- 29.1% fall in the 21-24 age range.
- 6.0% fall in the 25-30 age range.
- 9.3% fall in the 31-45 age range.
- The total sample size is 151 participants.

Gender:

- 51.7% of the participants are male.
- 45.0% are female.
- 3.3% fall under the category of "Other"
- The total sample size is 151 participants.

Educational Background:

- 4.6% of the participants are High School.
- 45.7% are bachelors school.
- 23.2% are Masters Degree.
- 26.5% fall under the category of "Other"
- The total sample size is 151 participants.

Cronbach Alpha

Table 1 : Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.686	13

Source: SPSS Software

As the alpha value is more than 0.07 i.e 0.686 the data is reliable

Hypothesis Testing:

Chi-Square Analysis

H1: There is significant association between age of respondent and I use social media platforms [eg. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter] regularly.

Age * I use social media platforms

Table 2. Crosstab: Age * I use social media platforms [eg. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter] regularly

Count		I use social media platforms [eg. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter] regularly.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	18-20	4	1	39	32	8	84
	21-24	2	2	8	22	10	44
	25-30	0	0	3	5	1	9
	31-45	4	0	2	4	4	14
Total		10	3	52	63	23	151

Source: SPSS Software

Table 3. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.355 ^a	12	.003
Likelihood Ratio	26.078	12	.010
Linear-by-Linear Association	.057	1	.811
N of Valid Cases	151		

- a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5.
- b. The minimum expected count is .18.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and i use social media platforms [eg. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter] regularly.

H2: There is significant association between age of respondent and I am aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media.

Age * I am aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media.

Table 4. Crosstab: Age * I Am Aware of Watch Brands Due to Their Presence and Promotion on Social Media

Count		I am aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	18-20	3	3	42	31	5	84
	21-24	2	2	10	22	8	44
	25-30	1	0	3	5	0	9
	31-45	5	1	2	2	4	14
Total		11	6	57	60	17	151

Source: SPSS Software

Table 5. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	39.497 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	34.015	12	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	.818	1	.366
N of Valid Cases	151		

a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H2. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and i am aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media

H3: There is significant association between age of respondent and social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands.

Age * Social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands.

Table6. Crosstab: Age * Social Media Marketing Has Influenced My Perception of Watch Brands.

		Social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	18-20	2	3	28	43	8	84
	21-24	2	4	12	23	3	44
	25-30	0	0	3	5	1	9
	31-45	3	0	3	4	4	14
Total		7	7	46	75	16	151

Source: SPSS Software

Table 7. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.156 ^a	12	.064
Likelihood Ratio	16.400	12	.174
Linear-by-Linear Association	.347	1	.556
N of Valid Cases	151		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .42.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H3. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands.

H4: There is significant association between age of respondent and I am more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social media.

Age * I am more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social media.

Table 8. Crosstab: Age * I Am More Likely to Consider Purchasing a Watch From a Brand I've Seen on Social Media

		I am more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social media.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	18-20	3	0	37	27	17	84
	21-24	3	1	13	22	5	44
	25-30	0	2	1	4	2	9
	31-45	5	0	2	2	5	14
Total		11	3	53	55	29	151

Source: SPSS Software

Table 9. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	51.989 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	35.937	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.076	1	.150
N of Valid Cases	151		

a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H4. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and i am more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social media.

H5: There is significant association between age of respondent and the quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands.

Age * The quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands.

Table 10. Crosstab: Age * the Quality of Content and Visuals on Social Media Impacts My Interest in Watch Brands.

		The quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	18-20	0	3	36	35	10	84
	21-24	3	4	5	21	11	44
	25-30	1	2	1	4	1	9
	31-45	5	0	4	4	1	14
Total		9	9	46	64	23	151

Source: SPSS Software

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	48.253 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	42.553	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.433	1	.006
N of Valid Cases	151		

- a. 11 Cells (55.0%) Have Expected Count Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Count Is .54.

Interpretation: As the p value is greater than 0.05, hence we reject H5. This shows that there is no relationship between age of respondent and the quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands.

DISCUSSION

The demographic data sample shows the core characteristics of the respondents, as age shows major participants belong to the age group of 18-20 which is 55.64%, and remaining age groups of 21-24 and 25-30 have smaller proportion of 28.9% and 5.9%. In the data collected gender distribution is fairly balanced with ratio of male at 51.7% and female at 45.0% (Vidani J. N., 2016). And the data regarding educational background of the respondents shows that majority of participants fall under category of high school (4.6%), while 45.7% are bachelors degree, 23.2% are masters degree and 26.5% falls under the other category (Vidani & Singh, 2017). By the reliability test, we get moderately satisfactory results of 0.686 (Vidani & Pathak, 2016).

According to the analysis, there is no significant relationship ($p = 0.000$) between age of respondents and aware of watch brands due to their presence and promotion on social media. (Vidani J. N., 2020). Hence, H2 is rejected, this shows that recommendations and aware of watch brands is not influenced by age (Vidani J. N., 2018).

According to the analysis, there is no connection ($p = 0.064$) between respondents' age and social media marketing has influenced my perception of watch brands. (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). Thus, H3 is rejected, it means that social media marketing of watch brands is not affected by the age of the participants (Vidani, Meghrajani, & Siddarth, 2023).

According to the analysis, there is no significant association ($p = 0.000$) between age and more likely to consider purchasing a watch from a brand I've seen on social

media. (Rathod, Meghrajani, & Vidani, 2022). Hence, H4 is rejected, which suggests that the brand I've seen on social media is not influenced by age (Vidani & Das, 2021)

According to the analysis, there is no relation ($p = 0.000$) between respondents' age and the quality of content and visuals on social media impacts my interest in watch brands. (Vidani J. N., 2022). Consequently, H5 is rejected, showing that social media impacts my interest in watch brands is not influenced by age of the participants (Saxena & Vidani, 2023).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This includes demographic summaries and subsequent analyses of the sample to provide a broader and more relevant understanding of the group, in which age and educational attainment play a significant role in shaping social media behavior. While this study did not find a significant association between age and any brand perceptions of social media viewing, these findings emphasize the complexity of factors influencing consumption behavior and the multi-bird approach when exploring the intersection of demographic social media brand perceptions.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Impact of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness of Watches in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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